

COMPUTER SCIENCES

EMOTION CLASSIFICATION USING MACHINE LEARNING METHODS

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Abstract

This article studies the problem of automatic classification of emotions using human facial expressions, and compares various machine learning algorithms, in particular k-NN, SVM, Random Forest, MLP and CNN, with the widespread FER2013, KDEF RAFDB and AffectNet databases and a single database created on their basis. Geometric and image-specific features were formed and recognition was performed using facial features and visual cues. The results obtained showed that the CNN model has high accuracy. It was also proved that data augmentation, ensuring class imbalance and selecting effective architectures are important factors in emotion classification. The results of this research can be used in areas such as human-computer interaction, education, and psychology.

Keywords: emotion, facial expression, machine learning, CNN, neural network, classification, database, automatic recognition.

Introduction

The classification of human emotions is one of the important and relevant research areas in such fields as information technology, psychology, human-computer interaction, healthcare, and security. Accurate and rapid identification of emotions allows for the assessment of human emotional states, the early detection of fears, the enhancement of interest and desires in education, and the understanding of human emotions by virtual assistants [1-3].

Emotions are expressed through subtle changes in the human face and voice, body movements, and physiological signals. The most widely studied method for detecting emotions based on facial expressions is the Facial Action Coding System (FACS). FACS is a system for analyzing and classifying human facial movements, developed by American psychologists Paul Ekman and Wallace Friesen [4]. It analyzes the movements of facial muscles and encodes each emotion based on action units (AUs). Each AU represents the movement that occurs when a specific muscle or group of muscles on the face is activated. This system allows us to detect emotions, reactions, and even false states through human facial expressions. The combination of action units can determine what kind of emotion, reaction, or facial movement a person is experiencing.

Machine learning is a set of algorithms that allow automatic learning based on available data, identifying patterns and making predictions based on them. This technology allows not only to increase the accuracy of emotion detection, but also to work in real time, to use multi-source data, and to create models specific to a person [5].

In recent years, the use of neural networks, in particular convolutional neural networks (CNN) and recurrent models (LSTM), has provided excellent results in emotion classification. Studies have shown that emotions can be recognized with an accuracy of 90% or higher using 20–35 specific points on the human face [5-9].

This article presents ways to form a set of features necessary for emotion classification and recognize emotions based on them using machine learning methods (such as k-NN, SVM, Random Forest, and MLP). The purpose of the study is to compare the effectiveness of various algorithms based on the proposed set of features and determine the most suitable method for application in real conditions.

Theoretical foundations

The issue of understanding and automatic detection of human emotions is relevant not only for com-

puter science, but also for psychology, neurophysiology, education and medicine. Emotion is the main psycho-emotional component of human thinking, speech and social relations, it is a set of reactions that are formed in response to situations in the human inner world and changes in the external environment. Emotion reflects the internal psycho-emotional state of a person and is expressed through facial expressions. Facial expressions are the most powerful, reliable and universal source of expression of emotions [5, 7].

In psychology, emotion is studied not only as a mental state, but also as a mediator between conscious and unconscious mental processes, impressions and actions. There are several theoretical approaches to classifying emotions, and one of the most widely used models is the theory of "basic emotions" developed by Paul Ekman. According to him, there are six emotions that are naturally and universally expressed on the human face: joy, sadness, anger, fear, disgust and surprise [4]. Later, Plutchik's models expanded the number of these emotions and showed the interrelationships between them [10]. According to classical theories, joy, sadness, anger, fear, disgust and surprise are the basic emotions. They are universal and occur in all people, regardless of gender, ethnicity, age and culture.

Emotion recognition is widely used not only in understanding the internal state of a person, but also in many areas such as education, medicine, and security [11].

The face is the most tangible and rich source of human emotions, and facial muscle movements allow for a complete and reliable expression of emotions. FACS is used to standardize and analyze these movements. Various combinations of emotions are formed based on FACS. In order to adapt complex facial movements to machine learning, geometric signs are generated based on special points (landmarks) [9].

Identifying specific points on a human face is the first step in automatic emotion recognition systems. Using the Dlib and Mediapipe libraries, it is possible to distinguish between 68 and 468 facial points [6, 12]. The distances, angles, and symmetry relationships between the obtained points form a feature vector representing facial expressions. For example, parameters such as the distance between the eyes and mouth, the degree of lip and mouth opening, and the height of the eyebrows are crucial in identifying emotions [5].

Facial landmarks and landmarks formation. The first step in automatic emotion recognition is to identify facial landmarks. These landmarks represent the geometric structure of the face and take into account movements in various parts of the face (opening of the lips, raising of the eyelids, scrunching of the nose, etc.). Typically, such landmarks are used as input data for artificial neural networks or classical algorithms.

Machine learning methods. Machine learning methods play an important role in emotion recognition. This involves automatic classification of various emotions based on human faces, voices, or biometric data [2]. The following machine learning methods are widely used in emotion classification:

K-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN). This is a simple but effective algorithm that classifies data based on its

nearest neighbors. In this method, proximity is calculated based on Euclidean, cosine, Manhattan, and other distances. The method works well on small data sets but slows down on large datasets.

Support Vector Machine (SVM). It constructs hyper-smoothness that maximally separates data in a large-dimensional feature space. It is an effective method for solving complex classification and categorization problems and can be further enhanced with polynomial and RBF kernels.

Decision Tree and Random Forest. Decision Tree builds paths based on data features and forms a classification model. Random Forest is an ensemble of many trees, each of which gives a different solution and makes a decision based on voting. This allows to reduce the risk of overfitting.

Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). This is a classic artificial neural network, consisting of fully connected layers. MLP allows for a high level of fine-tuning. When used correctly, it can achieve high accuracy with the required features.

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). CNN automatically generates image features. This architecture can also recognize micro-expressions on the face. CNN models (VGG16, ResNet50, EfficientNet) allow for direct image-based emotion classification.

Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) and LSTM. RNN and its extended version LSTM are used to detect time-dependent emotional changes. This method also has the ability to perform classification based on the dynamics of emotions across multiple frames in a video.

Evaluation criteria and metrics

It is very important to evaluate the performance of classifiers in machine learning, which uses the following metrics:

Accuracy: is one of the main metrics that shows how well a machine learning model classifies across all cases and is calculated as follows.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

where TP is True Positive, TN is True Negative, FP is False Positive, FN is False Negative.

Precision: A metric that indicates how many objects the model correctly identifies as actually belonging to the specified class and is calculated as follows.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

where TP is True Positive, FP is False Positive.

Recall: A metric that indicates how many true positive cases the model was able to identify and is calculated as follows.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

where TP is True Positive, FN is False Negative.

F1-score: Measures the degree to which Precision and Recall correlate with each other and combines these two metrics based on the harmonic mean. This metric is used in balanced scoring.

Confusion Matrix: A matrix that shows the correct and incorrect classifications for each class of a classification model, comparing the actual values and predicted values.

Using the above-mentioned metrics, the performance of different models is evaluated and suitable algorithms are selected.

Research methodology

Automatic recognition of human emotions based on facial expressions is a complex and multi-stage process, which consists of such components as data collection, processing, identifying informative features, creating a model, and evaluating the results. The main goal of this study is to classify emotions based on data obtained from facial special points through different machine learning methods and to determine which algorithm has the highest performance. For this, statistical and neural network-based models were used and their results were compared in the same database.

The study used the widely used FER2013, KDEF, RAFDB, and AffectNet databases that allow working with facial expression data.

The FER2013 database contains 48×48 facial expression images representing seven emotions. The images in these databases are collected from different age, gender, and ethnic groups, which serves to increase the generalizability of the models.

KDEF is a standard image database designed to study emotions through facial expressions, containing images of 35 men and 35 women each displaying 7 different emotions. The database contains more than 4,900 facial images, each of which is captured from multiple angles.

RAF-DB is a database of facial expressions, consisting of real-world facial images, spanning different ethnic groups, ages, and genders, taken from the Internet. The database contains over 30,000 images.

AffectNet is a database of over 1 million facial images automatically downloaded from the Internet, of which over 450,000 have been manually labeled.

The 68-point detector from the Dlib library and the 468-point detector from Google's Mediapipe FaceMesh were used to detect facial points in the images. These tools work effectively in real time and allow for an accurate representation of the geometric structure of the face. Based on the detected points, geometric features, distances between points, angles, ratios, symmetry indicators, and other statistical features, were calculated. The number of features was optimized by selecting 29–35 important points in the set of facial points that most closely correspond to a particular emotional state. After the set of features was formed, several machine learning algorithms were tested on them. From the classical statistical methods, the k-NN, SVM, algorithms were selected. Among these algorithms, SVM and RF stood out for their effectiveness. In addition, models based on artificial neural networks such as MLP were also studied. In the MLP modification, a 3-layer (128–64–32

neurons) architecture was chosen, the ReLU activation function and the Adam optimizer were used.

The work also used Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architectures for classification based not only on specific facial features, but also on the entire image. CNN models automatically learn features from images and do not require special work on how to shape them. A simple architecture with 2 Conv2D layers and MaxPooling elements was chosen in the study. The number of Epochs was set to 50, Batch Size — 64. To train these models, the FER2013 database was fully normalized, stored in grayscale format and assigned to appropriate classes.

The main metrics were used to evaluate the models. In addition, the Confusion Matrix was used to analyze the degree to which each emotion was correctly and incorrectly classified in the test. For example, images belonging to the "surprise" class were often classified as belonging to the "fear" and "joy" classes, which indicates that there are very similar features between some classes.

Data augmentation was performed, the generalization ability of the model was increased by methods such as image rotation, brightness change, and symmetry rotation. This allowed to increase the accuracy by an average of 2–4%. In addition, in order to restore class balance, artificial samples of some rare emotions were created using the SMOTE algorithm.

Using features based on facial features, SVM and MLP models achieved 74–77% accuracy on the FER2013 database, while the CNN architecture achieved about 82%. Geometric features based on facial features are an effective source for emotion detection, but deep learning models such as CNNs can achieve higher results by independently forming features from images. Therefore, a general approach, i.e., creating hybrid models by combining geometric features and image-based features, may be a promising direction.

Practical results

In this study, which is aimed at automatically classifying human emotions based on facial expressions, several machine learning algorithms were compared. All models were trained and tested on existing emotion image databases. Experimental studies were carried out in the Python environment, mainly using the Scikit-learn, TensorFlow, Keras and OpenCV libraries. First, the data was normalized, and facial special points were identified using Dlib and Mediapipe. Geometric features in the range of 70–100 were formed. Then, algorithms such as SVM, RF, MLP and k-NN were trained on them.

Accuracy results by model (%):

№	Model	FER2013+KDEF+RAFDB+AffectNet (Accuracy)
1	k-NN (k=3)	63.2%
2	SVM (RBF kernel)	74.6%
3	Random Forest	71.8%
4	MLP (3-layer)	76.1%
5	CNN (2 Conv + Pool)	81.9%

Analysis of results
F1-score in the class (FER2013+KDEF+RAFDB+ AffectNet)

Emotion	SVM	MLP	CNN
Joy	0.77	0.82	0.89
Sad	0.69	0.71	0.78
Angry	0.73	0.75	0.83
Fear	0.62	0.67	0.74
Surprise	0.65	0.70	0.76
Disgust	0.66	0.68	0.72
Neutral	0.75	0.80	0.86

The CNN model distinguished similar emotions such as “fear” and “surprise” better than other models. The “neutral” emotion was easier to detect than the other classes because it is a less dynamic form of facial expression. Many models labeled “surprise” as “joy” or “fear.” This suggests that multimodal (voice + face) data is needed to train the model.

A confusion matrix was created to analyze how the models made classification errors. For example, the CNN model correctly classified the emotion "joy" 89% of the time, while "fear" was incorrectly classified as "surprise" 24% of the time. These results demonstrate the visual proximity of the emotions.

Conclusion

The issue of automatic recognition of human emotions through facial expressions is an important scientific and practical direction in computer vision, artificial intelligence, and human-computer interaction. In this study, emotion classification was performed using geometric features based on facial landmarks and deep neural networks working with direct images. A comparative analysis of several classical and deep learning machine learning algorithms was performed. Studies have shown that geometric features based on facial landmarks can represent human emotions to a high degree. Models such as SVM, MLP, and RF based on these features showed good results. In particular, the accuracy of the MLP model was about 76%. This confirms the need to develop an approach based on facial landmarks. At the same time, the CNN model achieved high accuracy in all tests. The accuracy of CNN in the resulting combination of databases was 81.9%.

During the study, the models also observed cases of incorrect classification of emotions in some cases. In particular, the probability of incorrect classification was high for closely related visual expressions such as “surprise” and “fear”. This situation shows that facial images alone are not enough to correctly understand emotional states, that is, additional sources such as voice, hand gestures, and contextual information should be involved in identifying human emotions. In addition, the development of hybrid models that combine facial features and image-based features can improve the efficiency of emotion classification, allowing for a more complete understanding of emotions by using additional features such as voice, body movements, and speech context in addition to the face.

Based on the results of the study, it can be said that the issue of creating optimized, fast and lightweight models for various devices is urgent. In this case, since automatic classification of emotions is associated with

personal data, it is necessary to comply with confidentiality and ethical standards. In general, this study, devoted to classifying emotions through facial expressions, demonstrated the current effectiveness of popular models and the need to use more universal and complex approaches in the future.

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